

INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN DURING INDEPENDENCE

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the specifics of the development of industry in Uzbekistan during the years of independence. The specifics of industrial development are analyzed from a socio-historical point of view.

During the years of independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has made great strides in socio-economic development. Even during the global financial and economic crisis of 2008-2009, the national economy of Uzbekistan was one of the fastest growing in the world. Since 2010, the annual growth rate of Uzbekistan's GDP has been at least 8%. At the heart of these positive results, recognized by experts of the world community, is the huge potential for socio-economic development of the country and targeted reforms based on the "Uzbek model" of transition to a market economy.

The transit potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan within Central Asia has a favorable economic and geographical location and plays a very important role in the mutual integration of the countries of

the subregion. At the same time, our republic has natural resources that create great opportunities for the formation and development of a diversified national economy. First of all, the mineral resource potential of our country deserves special attention. A total of 2,700 deposits of about 120 types of minerals have been discovered in Uzbekistan. In particular, Uzbekistan ranks 4th in the world in terms of gold reserves, 7th in terms of uranium, 8th in terms of molybdenum and 10th in terms of copper. . Natural gas is the most important fuel and energy resource, and Uzbekistan ranks 14th in the world in terms of its reserves. Noru is one of the world's leading producers of potassium salts and phosphorites. Navoi, Tashkent, Kashkadarya, Bukhara regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan are rich in large

deposits of various minerals. This means that the huge reserves of mineral resources create ample opportunities for the development of non-ferrous metallurgy, fuel, chemical and building materials industries in our country.

Our country has agro-climatic resources that create favorable conditions for agricultural development. Due to the length of the growing season, the abundance of hot and sunny days, cotton growing and gardening in Uzbekistan. high-income agricultural sectors such as viticulture, vegetable growing, and horticulture are developing intensively. However, due to the fact that agriculture is developed mainly through artificial irrigation, the agriculture of the republic is strongly dependent on water resources. Tashkent, Andijan, Surkhandarya and Samarkand regions are relatively well supplied with this type of natural resources. The situation in Navoi, Bukhara and the Republic of Karakalpakstan, located in the west of the country, where a small part of the desert is occupied, is also complicated. However, despite the lack of water resources in our regions, Uzbekistan ranks 11th in the world in terms of irrigated land.

The population and labor resources of Uzbekistan are also the foundation of the country's socio-economic development. The population of our republic is constantly growing. The population of the republic increased from 20.2 thousand people in 1990 to 32.1 thousand people in 2017. In the post-2010 period, the birth rate in Uzbekistan was 23-24 per 1,000 people, the death rate was 5-6, and the natural increase was 18, or 1.8 percent. is happening. However, due to the fact that the residual migration is at a minimum negative level (-

0.1-0.2%), the overall population growth rate is 1.6-1.7%.

Over a short historical period, Uzbekistan has gradually and successfully solved such complex tasks as entering into international trade and economic relations, improving the structure of the national economy, developing industry, ensuring food, energy and transport security of the country.

In the dynamics of change in the GDP of the Republic can be divided into 3 periods. The first, 1991-1996, was characterized by an economic downturn. This was mainly due to the breakdown of the system of territorial division of labor within the former Soviet Union, cooperation between the sectors of the Uzbek economy and the economy of other republics. The second phase, from 1997 to 2003, was a period of stabilization of the national economy and the beginning of GDP growth. The third period began in 2004 and continues to this day. Over the years, Uzbekistan's GDP has been growing at a rate of no less than 8.0 percent.

Significant changes have also taken place in the structure of our national economy. First of all, it is noteworthy that the share of industry in GDP has grown significantly. In 1995, industry accounted for 17.1 percent of GDP, but in 2014 the figure rose to 26 percent. The share of agriculture in the national economy. respectively, from 28.1 percent to 17.6 percent. The structure of the industry has also changed significantly. The role and importance of electricity, fuel, chemicals, non-ferrous metallurgy, machinery and other heavy industries in the country's industry has grown, and the share of light industry, which in the pre-independence

period determined the republic's specialization, decreased by almost 3 times. The volume of industrial production in Uzbekistan has been growing steadily since the early 2000s, and the growth rate of the processing industry is several times higher than that of the extractive industries. As a result, at the end of 2016, the leading position in the structure of industry of the country was occupied by machine-building products with a share of almost 20%. pharmaceutical, sugar and other industries were built. Very large enterprises have been launched in the oil and gas-chemical industries. In the period since 2010, the Topalang HPP, Ustyurt Gas Chemical Complex, Khandiza Mining and Metallurgical Combine, Dehkanabad Potash Plant, Khorezm Automobile Plant, Zafarabad Cement Plant and other important production facilities have been completed. To date, Uzbekistan has a strong industrial production potential. Our country is one of the leading producers of gold, uranium, natural gas, cadmium, molybdenum, sulfuric acid, nitrogen fertilizers, fabrics, cars and other products in the CIS countries and around the world.

The regional structure of Uzbek industry has also changed. For example, in the late 1980s, the city and region of Tashkent accounted for 50 percent of the country's gross industrial output, and now these regions account for 30 percent. In turn, the share of Andijan, Kashkadarya, Navoi, Bukhara, Jizzakh regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan in the country's industry has increased significantly due to the establishment of a number of new enterprises. This means that the number of industrial centers in Uzbekistan is growing.

Uzbekistan's agriculture has also undergone significant changes. The priorities of the first reforms in agriculture were to end the cotton monopoly, to achieve grain independence, and to develop private farms and dehqan farms. Due to the sharp reduction in the area under cotton, the area under grain has increased 1.5 times. As a result, the gross yield of wheat in Uzbekistan has increased by 3.5-4 times, and in a short period of time the country has achieved grain independence. In addition, great attention was paid to the development of agricultural sectors such as vegetable growing, potato growing, horticulture, viticulture, dairy farming, which play an important role in ensuring food security of the country. As a result, over the years of independence, the yield of cotton has decreased from 5.5 thousand tons to 3.4 thousand tons, vegetables - 2.5 times, potatoes - 6 times, fruits - 4 times, grapes - 2.5 times, meat and milk production - 2 times. Today, Uzbekistan is one of the world's leading producers and exporters of grapes, melons and some fruits. In addition, the traditional agricultural sectors of Uzbekistan - cotton, silkworm, karakul - have not lost their importance. In particular, as of 2016, the country is the 6th largest producer of cotton in the world, the 3rd largest exporter, the 6th largest producer of silk, the largest producer of astrakhan leather. and in 2nd place.

Significant results have also been achieved in the development of the transport system. The most important of these is the achievement of the integrity of the railway transport system of the republic. Given the fact that the territory of Uzbekistan stretches for hundreds of kilometers from northwest to southeast,

and the state borders in a unique way through mountain ranges and vast deserts, this issue is of strategic importance. We are sure that Territory of Surkhandarya region Tashguzor Boysun Kumkurgan, Khorezm region and the Republic of Karakalpakstan Uchkuduk - Miskin Nukus, Fergana Valley Angren - Pop landi. As a result, the country's transport security and independence have been ensured. The Konimex-Miskin railway, which connects Navoi and Bukhara regions with the Republic of Karakalpakstan for a relatively short distance, and the railway from Urgench to Khiva, an international tourist center, are currently under construction.

In addition, significant work has been done in Uzbekistan to electrify the railways and build high-speed train routes. In particular, Afrosiyob on the Tashkent-Samarkand route, Nasaf on the Tashkent-Karshi route, and Sharq high-speed trains from Tashkent to Bukhara have been launched. Electrification of the Karshi-Termez, Karshi-Kitab and other railways has already begun. Upon completion, the geography of high-speed train routes in the country is expected to expand.

Also, in order to have reliable access to the seaports of the Republic of Uzbekistan in several directions, to realize the transit potential of economic and geographical growth through the connection with regional transport systems in different parts of Eurasia, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan Iston is establishing comprehensive cooperation with the Russian Federation, Khilai, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran and Oman. The first Termez Mazar-i-Sharif railway in Afghanistan, built with the help of our country, was the first stage in creating the shortest transport

route from Uzbekistan to the world's ocean ports in the southern direction. Unfortunately, the instability of the geopolitical situation in Afghanistan has indefinitely halted the construction of transport routes from the country to the Indian Ocean.

Extensive work in the transport system is an integral part of efforts to further develop the country's foreign economic relations. The Russian Federation, China, Kazakhstan, the Republic of Korea, Turkey and European countries are among the most important trade partners of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which has foreign economic relations with about 140 countries. The development of the transport system will allow expanding the foreign economic activity of the republic in new geographical directions.

The structure of the republic's exports has undergone significant changes during the years of independence. At the time of independence, the share of cotton fiber in the country's exports was 60%. In subsequent years, that number has steadily declined, dropping to 5 percent by 2016. In turn, the share of energy resources (primarily natural gas), non-ferrous metals, food and textile products, chemical products, and automobile production in the country's exports has grown significantly.

In recent years, a number of free economic zones (FEZs) have been established in the country at the initiative of the Government of the Republic in order to increase the industrial production and export potential of the regions, to attract more foreign industry to our national economy. First "Navoi", "Angren", "Jizzakh" (with a branch in Syrdarya region), then "Hazorasp" in Khorezm region, "Gijduvon"

in Bukhara region, "Urgut" in Samarkand region and "Kokand" in Fergana region. ELZs were created. To date, hundreds of new production projects are being implemented in these regions with the participation of domestic and foreign investors.

Prospects for socio-economic development of Uzbekistan depend on the rational use of the potential of each district and region of the republic in the national and regional interests.

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